

*Responsible Research and Innovation approach for transitioning
the traditional industry regions into digitalised industry territories.*

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DEFINITIONS & ACRONYMS

DEFINITIONS

Digitisation

Digitisation is the technical process of converting analog signals into a digital form, and into binary digits. (Tilson et al. 2010 and Hess 2019).

Digitalisation

Digitalisation is the use of digital technologies to change a business model and provide new revenue and value-producing opportunities; it is the process of moving to a digital business. (Gartner Glossary, <https://www.gartner.com/en/information-technology/glossary/digitalization>).

Digitalised Industry

The term “digitalised industry” stands for “Industry 4.0” (UNCTAD/DER/2019). Industry 4.0 is the digital transformation of manufacturing and production and further related industries and value creation processes. Industry 4.0 is used interchangeably with the fourth industrial revolution and represents a new stage in the organization and control of the industrial value chain. Culot et al. (2020) deal intensively with the background and the context and investigate the literature regarding “Industry 4.0”^[1]. They discuss it on various levels. Summing up the following description can be applied in DigiTeRRI: We refer to an industry as digitalised if its companies have predominantly changed their business models and provided new revenue and value-producing opportunities through the use of digital technologies.

Digital transformation

Digital transformation is a strategy to profoundly adapt/transform business activities, processes, competencies and models so that the opportunities of digital technologies are leveraged and can exert their impact across society. It affects the dimensions of strategy, leadership, products, operations, culture, people, governance, and technology. Within an organization, digitalisation can be characterised as proceeding along increasing maturity levels (Azhari et al. 2014) from being either “unaware”, “conceptual”, “defined” and “integrated” to finally “transformed”.

^[1] Industry 4.0 definitional elements have been identified analysing almost 100 academic and non-academic papers as sciencedirect tells (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0925527320300050?via%3Dihub>).

ACRONYMS

EU	European Union
R&I	Research and innovation
RRI	Responsible research and innovation
S3	Smart Specialisation Strategy

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Work package 2 settles the conceptual definitions and delineations, collects empirical R&I ecosystem data and provides an in-depth mapping of the involved traditional industry territories in their transition towards digitalised industry regions. The first task (T2.1) in this work package conceptualizes the empirical work to define the R&I ecosystem indicators that are relevant for the digitalisation process and the multi-faceted relation with the RRI dimensions.

The overall objective of the DigiTeRRI project is to develop a framework with specified actions the participating territories need to address in order to transition from traditional industry regions into digitalised industrial regions with self-sustaining and responsible R&I ecosystems. It does so by exploring three aspects or dimensions, firstly the RRI approach and how the RRI approach will support digitalisation transition process by implementing adequate RRI strategies into the regional policies. Secondly, by establishing self-sustaining R&I ecosystem, and thirdly, the degree of maturity of digitalisation in which each the territories currently find itself in.

The mapping and data process are outlined and introduces the indicators used within the dimensions of RRI, self-sustaining ecosystems, and digitalisation. The methodological approaches used within the mapping process are both quantitative and qualitative in order to triangulate the findings and provide a deeper and holistic understanding of the changes taking place in the territories. The rationale for this is so that findings can be compared between the territories as well as learn from each other of what practices may work.

The conceptual framework sets the theoretical and conceptual understanding of the dimensions used. Digitalisation, R&I Sustainable Ecosystems, and RRI is discussed and explored. Digitalisation policy and processes in a multi-level governance perspective introduced as actors participating are positioned at different levels in society and there is a spread of stakeholders from public administration, policy makers and politicians, business and industry as well as from civil society. How one can measure the degree of digitalisation in companies is also discussed. As the current economic system is based upon economic growth R&I ecosystem indicators are introduced and how one can understand these complex organisms as self-sustaining. Because one of the aims of the project is to introduce a deeper degree of RRI in the digitalisation part of regional policies within the participating territories RRI is further reviewed. How can the RRI dimensions of public engagement, science education, open access, ethics, and governance be both viewed and illustrated within the digitalisation part of regional policy is introduced.

The conceptual framework also provides a brief outline of how the DigiTeRRI project will continue after the mapping process through its visioning, and through the development and implementation of a road map in each of the territories.

1 INTRODUCTION

The digital transformation presents a unique opportunity for implementing, shaping, and embedding RRI at the regional level. Once systems, institutions, and policies of R&I in the digitalised economy become institutionalised they will be difficult to change. It is therefore imperative and a timely opportunity to promote responsible R&I practices actively and that is the mission of DigiTeRRI project, one overall aim is to assist policymakers and other stakeholders in seizing this opportunity and transform from triple-helix cooperation to quadruple helix cooperation within digitalisation.

The DigiTeRRI project focuses on three territories – Région Grand Est, Värmland, and Styria – which are territories with traditional industries such as steel or paper production, automotive industry, or aerospace supplier industry are familiar with a situation in which the businesses are global, but their societal impact is local. Nevertheless, such territories can only survive if they learn how to adapt to the changes in their industries and how to create valuable high-tech niche products. Many of these territories were shaped by their historical orientation to heavy industry. Most of them have been struggling since the 1980s with changing their regional orientation, for developing a sustainable economic system by specialisation in new technology fields using digitalisation. These territories are currently undergoing the change from the traditional industrial production to a digitalised industry, which brings a lot of new opportunities to the territories. However, experts also raise concerns that organisations might be unable to adapt to this fourth industrial revolution and influencing and changing all spheres of daily life affecting society, cultures, economic systems, and the industries. Thus, the project DigiTeRRI elaborates with stakeholders ranging from policy makers, research and education communities, civil society, to business and industry, a framework and develops a roadmap for a responsible transition of traditional industry regions into digitalised industrial self-sustaining R&I ecosystems by using Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach. The co-creation of the framework, the road-mapping process, and the implementation of actions will take place with partners and their stakeholders from three territories.

Territories with a long traditional industry such as in ironworking or in paper industry have generated specific infrastructure and culture in their regions. They are competitive on the global scale, because of their expert knowledge and their collaboration with universities. However, such industries face very hard competition globally today and in the near future due to the rapid change of digitalisation. Nevertheless, these industries can compete globally if they can manage to be highly innovative regarding knowledge, process, creating attractive jobs, and infrastructure within their regions, using their existing R&I ecosystems and their societies (e.g. employees with their family, the youth in these territories). Part of the DigiTeRRI goal is to strengthening and supporting the participating territories to become more attractive, responsible, resilient digitalised industrial territories. The three

territories engaged in DigiTeRRI, Värmland in Sweden, Grand Est in France, and Styria in Austria, are participating because of their similarity in:

- Their existing industries are traditional industries, for example paper, steel, iron and other materials and production industries;
- They are facing the challenge of digitalisation in their production systems and business processes and therefore, confronted with an even harder competition on the globe;
- They offer most of the jobs in the region - so they have a massive impact on region and social structure;
- Their close collaboration networks “industry – university – government” so that the R&I ecosystem has a good foundation;
- Their ability to get multi-actors in their own region to become partners of the consortium of DigiTeRRI; and
- Their experience in managing to attract and organise quadruple helix representatives, including the citizens, in workshops.

1.1 Région Grand-Est, France

This administrative region in Eastern France spans an area of 57,433 km² and has a population of 5.5 million inhabitants. Bordering Belgium, Luxembourg, Germany and Switzerland, it is a traditional industry area that superseded the former administrative regions of Alsace, Champagne-Ardenne and Lorraine. Industry represents 19.2 per cent of the added value at regional level and includes materials (15 per cent of national production), mechanics, textiles, chemicals and the agri-food sector. Auto giant PSA has three plants in the region.

The Région Grand Est has embraced industrial digitalisation and its Regional Council has implemented an ambitious collaborative strategy to support companies in the transition towards Industry 4.0, fostering investment (AMI Industry of the future) and strengthening the relationships between traditional industries, digitalised industries and RTD performers (AMI numérique). The development and reinforcement of trans-regional cooperation on topics such as AI (European Valley of AI), materials and processes, e-health or energy transition are also a priority for the local authorities, alongside smart specialisation strategy (S3). The Région Grand Est and its Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Grand Est joined efforts in 2018 to create Grand E-nov, the innovation agency that aims to provide services to the region’s companies and foster innovation.

Competitiveness clusters were first created in France in 2004 and are formed by companies, research laboratories and training institutions in well-identified areas that focus on specific themes and work alongside national, regional

and local authorities. Six clusters are active in Région Grand Est today, and these are focused on materials and processes (Materialia), health and MedTech (Biovalley France), Construction (Fibres-Energivie), water (HYDREOS), mobility (PVF) and bio-resources (IAR). They are based on a triple helix structure that combines enterprises, RTD performers/TTOs and regional stakeholders, and most work on an international level. Région Grand Est also runs a network of regional clusters which are focused on textiles (Pôle Textile Alsace) and agri-food (ARIA).

The Région Grand Est educates more than 206,000 students (8.1 per cent of the French student population and 9.2 per cent of French engineering students) at five universities: Strasbourg, Lorraine, Reims-Champagne-Ardenne, Haute-Alsace, and Troyes as well as in Engineering Schools. National R&I organisations include INRIA (National Institute for Research in Digital Science and Technology), CNRS (National Scientific Research Centre), INSERM (National Institute of Health and Medical Research), and CEA (Atomic Energy Commission) through CEA Tech.

1.2 Värmland, Sweden

Värmland is a region located in west-central Sweden and borders Norway; its proximity to Oslo is a significant factor both for the region's business and for its employment. The region faces complex societal challenges, for example but not exclusively a slow population growth (with a total of some 274,691 inhabitants, it has only grown by 0.5 per cent since 2009), low educational levels, low wages, and a lack of employment opportunities in comparison to the national average. Much of the population lives in remote rural areas, thus companies depend on effective communication networks. The region is home to large tracts of forestland, which are promoted as an asset for the forest industry and local economy. Värmland's economic activity is concentrated in a few dominant industries: pulp and paper, with approx. 4,000 employees; IT, with 2,000 employees; steel and engineering, with 10,000 employees; and the fastest-growing industry, tourism, with 3,000 employees.

The Värmland region firmly embraced the European Commission's Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisation (RIS3) in a bid to influence regional and national policies as well as to facilitate participation in other European-driven programmes such as Interreg, ESF, EJFLU, Cosme and Horizon 2020. This is done in conjunction with Europe 2020, the Swedish national innovation strategy, the national Swedish government's research and innovation proposal, the Swedish National Strategy for Regional Growth and Attraction 2015-2020, and the local Värmland strategy. The Värmland Academy for Smart Specialisation is a key tool in implementing RIS3, and the Värmland Academy for Smart Specialisation aims to utilise research for the benefit of industry, the County Administration, the Region of Värmland and its municipalities while strengthening the region's research environments.

There are four clusters in Värmland, each with their own organisation: steel and engineering (Steel and Engineering), ICT (Compare), forest-based bioeconomy (Paper Province), and the emerging tourism cluster (Visit Värmland). Innovation platforms and the Innovation Park bring companies and organisations related to research, innovation and SME development together, while the Technical Research (SP) has been established in the region. While Värmland is described as a “follower” region in terms of innovation, it is still ahead of the EU average in this area.

The Värmland region applies the RIS3 strategy for gender integration, analytical and mapping procedures have been implemented to raise awareness of the issue throughout the innovation and corporate ecosystem, while studies have been conducted to ensure that gender is prioritised in the development of future policies.

Karlstad University (KAU) offers some 16,000 students access to programmes in humanities, social science, natural science, technology, teaching, health care, and the Arts at its campuses in Karlstad and Arvika. Its research groups collaborate successfully with H2020 projects and academic partners, while its Grants & Innovation Office also connects researchers with major national and international companies such as Billerud Korsnäs, Stora Enso and Uddeholm, or public bodies such as Region Värmland.

1.3 Styria, Austria

The federal province (Bundesland) of Styria is located in the south of Austria. The region has a population of 1,2 million inhabitants and covers about 16,400 km². The biggest economic sector in Styria is the services industry, which accounts for 70.1 percent of the entire economically active population followed by 25.7 percent working in industry and trade. The main business sectors are machinery industry, automotive industry, pulp and paper, iron and steel production, materials, and electronic industry. Upper Styria is an Alps territory, in former times characterised by iron or mining and metallurgy. Today, many large companies as well as SMEs have settled in the area. The focus on material production has also attracted other branches such as polymer engineering, industrial logistics or environmental engineering. The economic crisis in the past led to a heavy loss of jobs in the region of Upper Styria, which resulted in a decrease in population as younger people have moved to urban areas, and that is a trend that continues today.

In the local government’s economic strategy for the period, leading up to 2025 (dated 2016) ‘digitalisation’ is one of the five main principles. It also highlights S3 policies that aim to lead the area into the future: technology and creativity, innovation and quality of life, digital transformation, the area as an attractive business location or bridging the gap between strategic planning and making the future a reality. Digitalisation is also one of the seven main

topics of the Styrian Green Book 2030+ focussing on smart communication, smart cities and regions, smart mobility, smart health and Industry 4.0 (smart production and services).

Styria is considered a robust economic player as well as an innovative, forward-looking area with the potential to anticipate and adapt to the changes caused by new trends such as digitalisation. With a research quota of more than 5 per cent, Styria is a leader among Europe's research-oriented regions. Styria has set up a profound cluster and network strategy. One of the territory's strengths is its strong collaborative network among science, industry and public organisations, reflected for example by the fact that Styrian partners are involved in 25 of 42 Competence Centres for Excellent Technologies (COMET). Furthermore, several universities are highly engaged in research projects promoting new technologies. All over Styria technology parks are situated to support innovative businesses with a common field of expertise not only with up-to-date infrastructure but also with extensive services. Universities and their start-up centres have promoted a lively entrepreneurial culture and a new orientation of technology in the territory.

Today, the number of employees in the Styrian region who have successfully completed the Matura exams at the end of their secondary education is lower than the Austrian average, and the gender pay gap continues to be an obstacle to gender equality. In Upper Styria, there is a lower employment rate among women than men. In 2017, the general employment rate for women was around 40 per cent, with less than 35 per cent in industrial sectors. On the other hand, the rate of women engaged in technology-oriented studies is constantly rising.

In Styria, higher education plays a major role. Styria's five universities and universities of applied sciences offer a profound education for more than 60, 000 students. Furthermore, HTL (Schools for Higher Technical Education) provide the industry with well-trained young employees.

1.4 Overall Objective of DigiTeRRI

The overall objective of the DigiTeRRI project is to develop a framework with specified actions which the participating territories need to address in order to transition from traditional industry regions into digitalised industrial regions with self-sustaining and responsible R&I ecosystems. It does so by exploring three aspects or dimensions, firstly the RRI approach and how the RRI approach will support digitalisation transition process by implementing adequate RRI strategies into the regional policies. Secondly, by establishing self-sustaining R&I ecosystem, and thirdly, the degree of maturity of digitalisation in which the territory currently find itself in. The indicators used to measure how much RRI currently exist within the territory, R&I self-sustained ecosystem, and level of digitalisation maturity are further outlined in the next chapter *Mapping and Data Collection*.

2 MAPPING AND DATA COLLECTION

The aim of this chapter is to outline the indicators in the mapping exercise of the R&I ecosystems and the RRI indicators in the three territories. The mapping will provide a visualisation of the three territories and provide a possibility for comparison which in turn can lead to a thematic focus for the stakeholders within the regions. The findings can describe a list of practices taking place within the regions and provides guidelines on how to proceed in the continuation in the transition process.

The data collection process for the mapping process will be outlined in this chapter. The R&I ecosystem indicators are discussed in chapter 4 and the RRI indicators are discussed in chapter 5. The data collection process is both quantitative and qualitative in its methodological approach. The quantitative collection of data will provide the information for the DigiTeRRI project to define the R&I ecosystem indicators that are relevant for the digitalisation process and the multi-faceted relation with the RRI dimensions. These indicators cover the socio-economic profile, research, development & innovation (RD&I), Regional Innovation Scoreboard, activities linked with digitalisation and innovation policies and governance structures. This activity shall provide a template for a complete regional profile that allows for cross-territorial comparison and interpretation, as well as identify in which areas of the territory's digitalisation transformation process in relation to the RRI indicators.

Simultaneous with the quantitative data collection in relation to the indicators of the R&I ecosystem, the digitalisation process within the territory, and the RRI activities a stakeholder identification process is taking place. Which, in each territory, are the stakeholder and which role do they have in the forming and implementation of digitalisation strategies and policies? Once the stakeholders are a descriptive statistical and network analysis method will be used to visualise the network connections in the three territories. The results may provide potential key action fields for RRI practices and to help identify mutual cross-territorial learning among involved stakeholders both within Région Grand Est, Värmland, and Styria as well as between the territories resulting in new ways of working around digitalisation strategies, policies, and in moving from a triple helix to quadruple helix model. As a corollary of the quantitative data collection there will also be a qualitative process of data collection, which will be described further in the later part of this chapter.

The data collection processes within DigiTeRRI are both drawing and modelled upon the experiences of gained from the SeeRRI project. The first objective of the DigiTeRRI project is to characterising and mapping the current three territorial R&I ecosystems. The creation of new knowledge is the basis for generating innovation thus in relation to digitalisation transformation processes it is a specific set of indicators in each set of the areas explored in the territories. The set of indicators within R&I ecosystems, digitisation, and RRI are outlined below.

R&I ecosystem indicators:

- a) *Human resources*: human resources in science and technology, numbers of employed;
- b) *Population*: number of persons residing in the territory;
- c) *Area*: total land area;
- d) *GRP*: Gross Regional Product, regional GDP;
- e) *Total R&D expenditures in % of GRP*: Total R&D expenditures with respect to institutional sector in % of GRP;
- f) *Number of patents*: Number of invention patents granted/applied for in respective region and reference period;
- g) *Number of publications*: Number of publications in respective region and reference period;
- h) *Urbanisation and agglomeration*: degree of urbanisation;
- i) *Transport infrastructure*: e.g. railway network, highway network, airports, harbours, passenger/freight traffic by mode of transport;
- j) *Number of firms*: the number of enterprises and/or local units active during at least a part of the reference period, and number of industrial enterprises above designated size;
- k) *Number of persons employed*: total number of persons in paid employment;
- l) *Number of universities*: a count of the number of universities active during at least a part of the reference period;
- m) *Number of R&D personnel of universities*: Total number of R&D personnel and/or researchers in universities;
- n) *Academic qualification*: Number of PhD students; Number of students enrolled in regular institutions of higher education;
- o) *Collaboration intensity*: Percentage of firms that engage in any kind of collaborations, and disaggregated by regional, national, and international firms, universities, and PROs;
- p) *EU-projects*: Number of EU-FP projects;
- q) *EU collaboration*: Network of regional participants and partners; and
- r) *Scientific profile*: activity profile measured by text analysis of publications.

RRI indicators:

- a) *Public engagement*:
 1. Models of public involvement in S&T decision making;
 2. Policy-oriented engagement with science;
 3. Public engagement performance mechanisms at the level of research performing organisations;
 4. Visiting science museums; and

5. Attending public meetings or debates about science.
- b) *Gender equality*: Share of research-performing organisations with gender equality plans;
- c) *Science education*:
 1. Importance of societal aspects of science in science curricula for 15 to 18-year-old students; and
 2. Citizen science activities in research performing organisations.
- d) *Open access*: Research-performing organisations' support structures for researchers as regards incentives and barriers for data sharing;
- e) *Ethics*: Ethics at the level of higher education institutions and public research organisations; and
- f) *Governance*: RRI-related governance mechanisms within research-funding and higher education institutions.

Digitalisation indicators:

- a) *Affordability*: activity profile measured by text analysis of publications;
- b) *Infrastructure reliability*: Investment per telecom subscriber such as mobile, broadband and fixed line;
- c) *Network access*: network penetration;
- d) *Capacity*: broadband speed;
- e) *Usage*: internet retail; e-Government;
- f) *Human capital*; engineers as % of total population; and
- g) *Industrial automation*:
 - 1) Automation and robotics;
 - 2) Prototyping; and
 - 3) Digital factory.

The quantitative mapping process of the DigiTeRRI project follow the same structure as the SeeRRI project, however with a different focus upon indicators. The process contains a general characterisation of the R&I actors in the respective territories – Région Grand Est, Värmland, and Styria – and their digital technological profile (as outlined by the various sets of indicators outlined) will show the region-internal knowledge base reflecting the region-internal capabilities that are important in relation to region-internal knowledge creation but also to enable access to region-external knowledge. As a result of the creation of new knowledge in the three participating territories also allows for learning from similar territories experiences.

The stakeholder identification process in the DigiTeRRI territories underlying aim is to provide a comprehensive overview of the general R&I ecosystem characterisation, the identification of the ecosystem's actors and interactions allows for the identification of potential stakeholders within RRI that needs to be included in future collaboration. In the characterisation process two methodological approaches are applied: 1) a general description

of the R&I ecosystem is provided by using a descriptive analysis and more important stakeholder actors are identified. 2) The interactions between the actors and stakeholders are then presented in network diagrams. Formally networks can be modelled through graphs and this in turn is an abstract object formed by set of nodes and links which connect the nodes, and the relationship between these nodes.

The data collected through the quantitative data collection processes described above will be triangulated and enriched through a qualitative data collection process. The triangulation process allows for 'cross-checking the existence of certain phenomena and the veracity of individual accounts by gathering data from a number of informants and a number of sources and subsequently comparing and contrasting one account with another in order to produce as full and balanced a study as possible' (Bell 1999:102). A rationale for this is to explore how the stakeholders within the respective territories view the maturity level of the territory, and what the next steps are in the digital transformation process within the territory. Key stakeholders will be identified in each region and in-depth interviews carried out with these stakeholders. The interviewees will be asked to identify practices within digitalisation, a practice is defined as the sum of activities carried out to achieve a result for the recipient by mobilising various resources. the practice must be objectified by tangible facts, that is to say observable phenomenon(s) proving its existence. As well as in which RRI-type approach can the practice be categorised? Questions in the semi-structured elite interviews will specifically explore digitalisation in relation to RRI indicators, the questions are:

- 1) Public engagement through the practice:
 - a) Users contribution;
 - b) Academic contribution;
 - c) Politic engagement; and
 - d) Public institutions engagement.
- 2) Gender equality:
 - a) Gender balance in the group piloting the practice;
 - b) Gender balance within all the beneficiaries; and
 - c) The gender equity is part of the practice itself.
- 3) Science education:
 - a) The practice integrates scientific training
 - b) The practice integrates scientific communication
- 4) Open access
 - a) The data and information produced are on open access;
 - b) Publications diffusion; and

- c) Practice mobilize social media and networks.

- 5) Ethics:
 - a) Conflict of interest;
 - b) Privacy respect;
 - c) Balance between risk and value;
 - d) Value creation equitable distribution; and
 - e) Respect of all contributors.

- 6) Governance:
 - a) Un-corporatist governance; and
 - b) Composite governance.

Through interviews the DigiTeRRI project can gain access to large amounts of data quickly, and immediately during the interview follow-up, and, if needed, clarification of answers given is possible. Elite interviewing is a specialised case of interviewing which focuses on a particular type of interviewee, to be precise elite individuals who are considered to be influential, prominent and well informed within their area. Elite interviewees are thus selected for interviews on the basis of their expertise in areas relevant to the project, the interviewees will be the identified key stakeholders in each territory. During elite interviews, the interviewees usually provide an overall view relevant to the research project. Elite interviewees can also act as a sounding board for the researcher, who may wish to test preliminary findings/conclusions drawn from earlier research and/or interviews.

The mapping of dominant indicators and stakeholders provides an illustration of the R&I digitalisation ecosystem of each territory, classified by its characteristics (typology of the territories), and making transparent the strengths of the three territories regarding RRI, economic, local dynamics, history, expectations, and requirements as well as specific concerns which will be foundation for the second objective of DigiTeRRI, namely that of generating a vision for each of the three territories and the thematic focus of this DigiTeRRI by applying this knowledge in the road-mapping process which is adopting the RRI approach to support the *responsible transition of traditional industry regions into self-sustaining digitalised industrial self-sustaining R&I ecosystems by using Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach.*

3 DIGITALISATION

As the overall objective of the DigiTeRRI project is to develop a framework with specified actions for the participating territories in transitioning from traditional industrial regions into digitalised industrial regions with self-sustaining R&I ecosystems as well as incorporating RRI into the regional policy actions the following parts of the conceptual framework will explore Digitalisation (this chapter), R&I sustainable ecosystem (chapter 4), and Responsible Research Innovation (chapter 5).

3.1 Digitalisation strategies in a multi-level perspective

Digital transformation, digitisation, and digitalisation are all frequently discussed in research with focus on economic development and is expected to have a significant impact upon companies and how they operate as well as on markets and as a consequence the wider economy. The three regions in this project – Grand Est, Värmland, and Styria – are all regions in member state countries of the EU. When a state become a member of the EU it delegates part of the decision-making authority to the institutions of the EU, the extent of the transfer of decision-making to the EU institutions and the role of the EU institutions in relation to the member states varies depending on policy area. How ‘politics and policies are done’ has thus changed and is now shared among more actors and levels in society. It has been argued that EU affairs, i.e. policies, have become part of the *daily politics* in the member states (Stegmann McCallion 2016). The member states thus find themselves within the EU as a multi-level polity². Within the academic literature this is often referred to multi-level governance. The multi-level aspect of the polity is understood as the political system in which the levels of society operate, in this case the supranational EU level, the national level, and the sub-national levels both regional and local. Thus, multi-level is itself self-explanatory. To this the *governance* aspect needs to be added, the reason for this is that the governing is taking place at all these levels as well as the change in many policies to include non-public actors into the policy process. The concept of governance includes non-governmental actors into the collective decision-making processes within a political system. Non-government actors are involved in the research and innovation policy processes. Thus, it can be argued that the theoretical framework of multi-level governance can be used to understand national and sub-national digitalisation strategies. Multi-Level Governance has been defined as a: ‘*co-ordinated action by the European Union, the member states and democratically elected regional representatives, based on partnership and aimed at implementing EU policies as the shared responsibility of the different tiers of government concerned*’ (Europaforum Norra Sverige 2009:1). As a result of being part of a multi-level political

² A polity is an organised society, a political system or entity.

system, and finding itself within the hierarchical policy structure, EU policy influence national policy which in turn influence regional policies.

Within a multi-level political system like the EU national digitalisation policies and strategies are either directly or indirectly influenced by the European Digital Strategy.³ Because the member states find themselves at different stages on the digital transformation index the national strategies and policies can have different aims and goals which in turn influence the regional digitalisation strategies within the regions (territories). In the IMD World Digital Competitiveness Ranking 2019 the three participating member states in DigiTeRRI Sweden is ranked as number 3, Austria as number 20, and France as number 24.⁴ Using the UN's EGDI, from 2018 which assesses e-government development at a national level and is based on three components: online service index, telecommunication infrastructure index and the human capital index, the three member states place themselves

³ The EU's digital strategy is fourfold, firstly it focuses upon *technology that works for people*, that is to say that the technology can make a real difference in the EU citizen's lives. Within this part of the digital strategy are areas such as digital skills and jobs, AI, cloud computing, blockchain, high-performance computing, quantum technologies, connectivity, 5G, IoT, cybersecurity, digital inclusion, photonics, and electronics. Technology should be used in a way that is shaped in line with European values. A second focus is upon providing a *fair and competitive digital economy*, within part of the central points are data, online platforms, eCommerce, copyright, digitising European industry, start-up Europe, and the Digital Economy and Society Index. What is important here is to enable a frictionless single market where business can compete on equal terms and the usage of digital technologies in order to be able to compete in the global economy, and that consumers can feel safe that their rights are respected. The third aspect of the digital strategy concerns the digital 'world' is open, democratic, and a sustainable digital society. Within this part of the strategy disinformation, media and digital culture, trust, ePrivacy, eHealth, eGovernment, smart cities, safer internet, and women in ICT. The rationale that by providing an environment in which the citizens feel both empowered and secure in how they act and interact online. The fourth foci are on the EU as a global digital player. The EU is committed to setting global standards for emerging technologies and by disseminating the norms and values of the EU within digitalisation and digital transformation of societies. The digitalisation has become part of the EU's foreign policy in relations with third countries, standardisation, and the next generation internet.

⁴ The IMD World Digital Competitiveness Ranking (WDCR) measures the capacity and readiness of 63 economies in the world. The ranking measures how the economies adopt to and explore digital technologies as a key driver for economic transformation in business, government and wider society. The structure of the WDCR measurement is constructed upon three factors; *knowledge* which refers to the intangible infrastructure and as such underlines the process of digital transformation through the discovery, understanding and learning of new technologies. The second factor *technology* assesses the overall context through which the development of digital technologies is enabled within the economy. The third factor is *future readiness* and this examines the level of preparedness of an economy to assume its digital transformation (Bris, Caballero, Cabolis, and Pistis 2019).

all within the bracket of having a very high EGDI. Sweden was ranked 6 (5 in the 2016 EDGI index), France was ranked 9 (10 in the 2016 EGDI index), and Austria was ranked 20 (16 in the 2016 EGDI index). A conclusion from this is that the three member states in the DigiTeRRI project are all advanced in the digital transformation processes, however there are differences within the member states and the regions find themselves at different stages in the digitalisation processes.

3.2 How to measure digitalisation in society

That the world and our societies are going digitisation and digitalisation process is not disputed, it has been described as the fourth industrial revolution. One way of measuring this digital transformation taking place in our societies and thus measuring cross-country progress is by using a digitisation index. This index consists of six elements and twenty-three indicators (for a full list of indicators is available in Katz and Koutroumpis 2013:216), which provides parameters that are measurable and thus comparable. The six elements are 1) affordability, 2) infrastructure availability, 3) network access, 4) capacity, 5) usage, and 6) human capital.

Table 1. Components and Subcomponents/Parameters of Digitalisation

Component	Subcomponents/Parameters
Affordability	Residential fixed line cost adjusted for GDP/capita Mobile cellular cost adjusted for GDP/capita Fixed broadband internet access cost adjusted for GDP/capita
Infrastructure reliability	Investment per telecom subscriber (mobile, broadband, and fixed)
Network access	Network penetration Coverage, infrastructure, and investment
Capacity	International internet bandwidth (kbps/user) % broadband connections higher than 2 mbps
Usage	Internet retail volume E-government usage % individuals using the internet Data as % of wireless ARPU Dominant social network unique visitors/month/capita SMS usage
Human capital	% engineers in labour force % skilled labour

Source: Katz & Koutroumpis 2013:315

The adoption of both mobile and fixed broadband networks account for accessibility as well as ownership of data devices. 'Affordability is essential and derives from the relative access of costs providing such access. Reliability of networks depends on the annual network investment per subscriber and the faults reported per line. Speed is proxied by the performance of country level international links and the capacity of wireline 'last mile' offerings. Usage is a key component of digitization and includes the utilization and adoption of all commercial activities, government services, social media adoption and data usage. Skills contribute to digitization both in terms of development of local service offerings and usage capacities' (Katz & Koutroumpis 2013:314).

Relevant parameters are included under each element of the digitisation index. Some of these parameters correspond the vectors identified within the digital transformation processes outlined by the OECD.

3.3 How to measure digitalisation in companies

OECD in its report *Vectors of digital transformation* outlines three key areas in which digital transformation is affecting how both society and the economy is operation. These are 1) scale, scope, and speed; 2) ownership, assets and economic value, and 3) relationships, markets, and ecosystems. In the report these areas are broken into vectors – or key properties – of digital transformation which cut through almost all policy domains in society as they are both intertwined and reinforcing. These vectors are intended to provide a framework to which already existing or new policies can be assessed in order to ensure the policy's is apt in the digital era.

In the area of *scale, scope, and speed* three vectors are found, these are 1) scale without mass, and here one can explore the role of core digital products and services such as software and data, and with the internet's global reach thus allowing companies a global market for its services and products, companies often with few employees and tangible assets. 2) Panoramic scope, the digitisation process facilitates the creation of complex products which combine many functions and feature such as the smartphone and thus enable extensive versioning, recombination and tailoring of services. And 3) speed, or dynamics of time. Technology allows the present to be easily recorded and thus the past to be probed, indexed, resold as well as remembered. Thus, it can be argued that institutional processes may be outpaced by digital activities and as a result influence procedures, behaviours and limit human attention. In the area of *ownership, assets, and economic value* there is one vector and this is intangible capital and new sources of value creation. The intangible forms of capital such as software and data are seeing greater investments, and platforms enable both companies and individuals to monetise and/or their physical capital more easily and as a result change the nature of ownership such as from goods to services. In the third area *relationships, markets, and ecosystems* the remaining vectors are found. These are 1) the transformation of space; software, data and computing resources which can both be stored and used anywhere in the world and as such is decoupled from borders. 6) Empowerment of the edges, users innovate, design and construct their own networks

and communities. And 7) platforms and ecosystems, the lower costs of digital interactions reflect the development which has resulted in that several of the largest platforms essentially serve as proprietary ecosystems with varying degrees of integration, interoperability, data-sharing, and openness (OECD 2019:6).

In order to understand the changes taking place and needed to take place within companies and industries further aspects needs to be added to make the changes applicable in order to further advance the digitalisation process within the business.

Sandhukul, Shilov, and Smirnov (2019) identified eight factors within the literature on digitalisation in companies and synthesised these dimensions. The dimensions are strategy, leadership, products, people, culture, operations, governance, and technology. The dimensions briefly in more detail:

- *Strategy*: a strategy that either creates awareness of or focus on digital transformation, thus expressing a precise target aims, the goal(s) can focus on improved customer focus, increased efficiency, internal processes or new business models.
- *Leadership*: the management should bring digitalisation, as the goals and focus within the strategy, into the business operations and enable employees to participate in the implementation of the digitalisation strategy.
- *Products*: the company's communication with customers is essential; the rationale for this is to competitiveness within the field or branch of operation.
- *People*: or the employees within a company, both tasks and role models should exist for employees in relation to the digital competencies needed. For this further training opportunities should be provided for the staff.
- *Culture*: a company's culture should be taken into consideration in processes of change. Due to the fact that the digitisation process of a company usually affects the whole company and all its parts it needs ensure transparency, communication and co-creation taking place within the business in order to keep momentum and a feeling of ownership among the whole organisation structure. In this process both external staff and customers could be included.
- *Operations*: with the new or increased digital orientation within the business, further elements of the business may have to be adapted in order to meet the goals of the digital strategy.
- *Governance*: as digital transformation activities should be both visible and controllable for the company the digital governance structure should help with a number of tasks. These tasks could be: mobilising resources, acquiring digital skills within the workforce, and

reducing system redundancies. It is thus important to have frameworks and guidelines in place as these are often used to this end. Furthermore, for many companies the process of digitisation should be assessable, which is why the digital strategy must according to Sandhukul, Shilov, and Smirnov be measurable through economic targets.

- *Technology*: within the field of technology use an essential task linked to digitisation is cross-channel interaction. Thus, providers of services should have an overview of all transactions, such as purchases/purchasing, and services for the customer. The business thus should treat each channel of interaction with potential and existing customers as negative customer experiences can have negative impacts on the company (Sandhukul, Shilov, and Smirnov 2019).

The last dimension *technology* has been described as *customer experience* by Gamache, Abdul-Nour, and Baril (2019). Thus, by assessing these dimensions, a degree of maturity in relation to digitalisation in companies can also be measured. The levels of maturity are unaware, conceptual, defined, integrated, and transformed as illustrated in the figure below.

		Maturity levels				
		Unaware	Conceptual	Defined	Integrated	Transformed
Dimension	1. Strategy	Strategic vision, transformation roadmap				
	2. Leadership	Management methods, sponsorship, resources				
	3. Products	Business model, innovation capabilities, digital value chain				
	4. Operations	Channels & business practices, processes, agility				
	5. Culture	Customer centricity, hierarchy vs. network, openness				
	6. People	Roles, expertise, capabilities				
	7. Governance	Communication & collaboration rules, KPIs, alignment				
	8. Technology	Software tools, cloud architecture, ICT infrastructure, Industry 4.0				

Source: Azhari et al. 2014: 38.

Figure 1. Digitalisation Maturity Levels

By exploring each dimension through a maturity lens a business, company and/or organisation can identify where further progress in relation to digitalisation is needed.

4 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION: ECOSYSTEM INDICATORS

The traditional understanding of an *ecosystem* is the environment of its interrelationships of the constituents within its unit of space, and within which the constituent parts function as one unit. When such a unit function well there is an equilibrium between the constituent parts. A research and innovation ecosystem models itself not on the natural science's ecosystem but on an economic model which enable development and innovation. The development can be in the areas of, for example, technology and/or service, and as result the focus is on economic prosperity and development. According to Jackson (2011) the constituent parts are that of actors and institutional entities within a geographical space, the actors and entities include both material and human resources. The differentiation between actors and institutional entities is that actors are seen as individuals and it is through their association with an organisation that makes the actor part of that institutional entity. What the actors can contribute to the research and innovation system, as already mentioned, are material and/or human resources. The material resources can be funding, facilities, and/or equipment, whereas the human resources can be personnel with specific knowledge and for higher education organisations for example researchers' specific knowledge. Human resources are also represented under knowledge as ideas, this is a characteristic of an innovation ecosystem in which peoples' ideas contribute to the evolution dynamic of the ecosystem. Ideas are thus concepts that are shared within the ecosystem. Institutional entities for example in our case are the public organisations Région Grand Est Regional Council, Region Värmland, and the local government of Styria, higher education institutions, cluster organisations Materialia, Paper Provice, and COMET, and businesses/industry. One major change in the composition of research and innovation ecosystem is represented by open innovation. The dynamic of research and innovation integrates external stakeholders as social networks, policy makers, communities, and open source contributors which generate new stakeholders and new practices within the research and innovation process.

The constituent parts of an ecosystem are a 'network of interconnected organisations' within a geographical space. An innovation ecosystem is thus a 'complex innovation of activities' (SeeRRI 2019) in which co-evolution between the different actors from political, economic, and technological spheres of society. Jackson (2011) argues that within an innovation ecosystem consists of two distinct types of economies which are separated from each other, there is on the one hand a knowledge economy and on the other hand a commercial economy. The knowledge economy is driven by research whereas the commercial economy is driven by the marketplace. The coupling between these two economies are weak and the reason for this is that part of the funding. Research and

development in the knowledge economy derive from tax revenues and thus the public purse, the other part of the funding derives from the commercial sector and through the involvement of companies themselves. One way of overcoming the weak coupling between the knowledge economy and the commercial economy is through research and responsible innovation. Even though the coupling may be weak between the two economies they are finding themselves in a virtuous – and dependent – circle. The commercial economy is reliant upon findings from research within the knowledge economy, and the knowledge economy research is contingent upon successful, and profitable, research and development investments and innovations in the commercial economy.

The current economic system, within which the European welfare states find themselves in and function, is built upon an economic model dependent upon economic growth. There is generally two ways of increasing an economic output and it is either by producing more using more resources or by using the same resources in new innovative ways thus getting a larger output for the same input, see for example new growth theory. In new growth theory a distinction is made between objects which are rival and ideas which are non-rival.⁵ Objects are traditional goods such as labour, capital, land or human capital. Whereas ideas are blueprints, design, or a set of instructions for starting with existing objects (Jones 2019). Thus, the onus upon developing innovation, innovation ecosystems, and sustainable research and innovative ecosystems.

4.1 SELF-SUSTAINING R&I ECOSYSTEMS⁶

According to Rinkinen (2016:53) ecosystems are ‘self-organising and complex systems’; and it is within these ecosystems that innovations and niche development may take place depending on involved actors from involved

⁵ As explained by Jones (2019:865) ‘the distinction between ideas and objects? Objects are rival: one person’s use of an object precludes the simultaneous use of the object by others. In contrast, ideas are nonrival: an idea can be used simultaneously by any number of people. If I use a machine, or a gallon of gasoline, or an hour of a doctor’s time, others cannot use the same thing; this is the sense in which objects are scarce. Indeed, economics is precisely the study of the allocation of such scarce resources. But any number of people can simultaneously use calculus and any number of assembly lines can use the design for the latest computer chip. New ideas are scarce in that we are always looking for better ideas, but existing ideas are not scarce in the same way that a building or a doctor is – and this has far-reaching consequences for economics.’ However, in C-K theory it is considered that that in the *concept space*, in which ideas belong, there is no ordering relationship on a mathematical point of view thus meaning that no idea is better than another one (Hatchuel, A. & WEIL, B 2002).

⁶ Three partners – AIT, WeDO, and Nordlandsforskning – of DigiTeRRI were part of the SeeRRI *Building Self-Sustaining Research and Innovation Ecosystems in Europe through Responsible Research and Innovation* and DigiTeRRI is building upon their findings regarding self-sustaining research and innovation ecosystems.

stakeholders from policy makers, academia, civil society, and business and industry. What is of importance then is that self-sustaining ecosystems find its actors from within a quadruple-helix cooperation within the geographical territory. The DigiTeRRI project work out from the same vision as the SeeRRI project, namely that self-sustaining R&I ecosystem are considered to:

1. be complex and self-organizing;
2. be flexible to niche development;
3. find innovation potential from interfaces & unexpected combinations;
4. provide platforms for development and foster peer-to-peer management;
5. provide access to global business ecosystems based on the local/regional innovation ecosystem;
6. be open to innovation, co-creation, users (Quadruple Helix cooperation); and
7. be trial-based, experimental, and apply rapid prototyping methods in the real world (SeeRRI 2019).

The goal of sustainable research and innovation ecosystems is to reach sustainability; however, this may be seen as a utopian goal that can never be reached as the sustainable research and innovation ecosystems should be viewed as ‘living’ organisms as an ongoing process. It is because actors are human beings, and as such person dependent, as parts of ecosystems contribute their knowledge, network contacts and other valuable human resources the ecosystem is in a constant flux and thus not being a static entity. What is of importance is then that within the research and innovation ecosystems one is aware of dominant norms within disciplines and/or industries and/or society, and how these dominant norms may be open or closed to new ideas and ways of working (Boly et al 2014). This is where responsible research innovation plays a crucial role a crucial role in the research and innovation process and the inclusion of stakeholders such as actors within policy makers, research community, education community, civil society, and industry.

5 RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH INNOVATION

Currently one can argue that the economy of European society is built upon two types, these two economies are the commercial one and the knowledge based one. It is the knowledge base one that is of more interest in this project DigiTeRRI when it comes to Responsible Research Innovation (RRI), however the commercial economy should also in their innovations take into consideration the aspects of RRI. The knowledge-based society has a main aim to find solutions to and overcome societal challenges. In order to overcome some societal challenges innovation is needed, these innovations can be a new method in decision-making processes and or implementation processes of policies, it can be new ideas within a field, and/or new services or products.

In relation to RRI the social and economic prosperity of an economy are dependent upon innovations and the innovation landscape. However, the social and economic prosperity should also be in line with the general values, needs, and expectations in society in general. What is meant here is that policy should be implemented with and for society engaging all actors i.e. educational and research institutions, civil society, business and industry, and policy makers. An implicit understanding of this is that the above-mentioned actors also are part of influencing the decision-making process with the result that a more inclusive and sustainable society.

5.1 Responsible Research and Innovation Indicators

In order to ensure that the policy process takes place incorporating the RRI perspective there is a set of RRI outlined and which should be taken into consideration. The indicators are public engagement, gender, equality, science education, open access, ethics, and governance. Each indicator will be explored in more detail below.

5.1.1 Public engagement

The role that public engagement⁷ can have in relation to RRI is that of aligning needs and expectations of wider society have on research and innovation, that is to say addressing the expectations-delivery gap. Public engagement thus serves as a bridge between wider society and the research and innovation communities. By involving wider society more already existing knowledge is being utilised in new ways but also opportunities for developing scientific questions addressing needs of society are further opened up. Which societal problems or issues are expected to be resolved and found solutions to? This element also correlates to the democratisation process of research and innovation, as discussed under governance, as the relevance of research carried out and

⁷ Available here <https://www.rri-tools.eu/public-engagement#>.

innovations for society are grounded in wider societal needs. The RRI toolkit in relation to public engagement have five different aspects:

- It widens and enhances the participation of society at all stages in the research and innovation processes;
- Public engagement leads to new partnerships;
- Ensures a trans- or multidisciplinary approach;
- It advances collaborative decision-making and a shared responsibility over research and innovation processes; and
- it promotes citizen science and open innovation.

Public engagement provides different challenges and opportunities for the various stakeholder groups. For policy makers one opportunity in relation to RRI is that it brings decisions on research and innovation policies closer to wider society thus anchoring these policies within wider society and through this further legitimising the research and innovation output from research and education communities. The research community can through this RRI indicator engage show how they engage citizens in research practices which may lead to more effective research and innovation processes in line with the needs of wider society. The role of the education community is to empower younger students and life-long learners to participate in research and innovation as well as in decision-making processes of research and innovation. A wider public engagement participation in research and innovation is key for responsible research innovation success. Civil society organisations engagement in the RRI process is crucial for the involvement when it comes to grounding the voice of wider society in the research and innovation processes, and this is making the process not only more democratic but it also provides a layer of public accountability in the research and innovation policies. Business and industry have a responsibility to engage other stakeholders when it comes to implementation of responsibility measures in relation their end-products and industrial processes as a result of research and/or innovation.

Public engagement thus provides an arena within RRI where societal challenges can be solved by a wide diversity of actors and as such gain a wider 'ownership' of solutions within wider society.

5.1.2 Gender equality

The gender equality⁸ aspect within RRI is around a fair representation which recognise diversity in society, more specifically the balance between men and women. There are structural explanations why men often are overrepresented within research and innovation environments. Research and innovation have to be able to be

⁸ Available here <https://www.rri-tools.eu/gender-equality#>.

applied to the whole population, and it should be responsive to peoples' – and society's – needs. The RRI toolkit on gender equality has six different features:

- Gender balances research teams should be promoted;
- Gender stereotypes should be broken down within society;
- Awareness needs to be further raised in relation to gender sensitive funding and investments;
- Gender-friendly workplace cultures should be ensured;
- The gender dimension should be considered in research and innovation; and
- There should be a gender balance in decision-making.

The features raise different challenges for the various types of stakeholders. For policy makers and politicians equality is of utmost importance at all political levels in society because it is one of the EU's fundamental values. As a fundamental value it should be included and promoted in all activities as well as in legislation initiated at the EU level and later implemented in the member states. The rationale for this is that research and innovation need to utilise the full use of all citizens, both men *and* women, whichever of the gender that is underrepresented the aim is to ensure a more even balance. When it comes to the research and education communities gender equality is a priority; this entails gender equality balanced research teams and the challenging of gendered stereotypes within sciences also at early stages of education, for example in primary education, as well as ensuring a gender balance in decision making in relation to research and education but also the research and innovation policies. For example, is an objective in the European Commission's strategy on promoting gender equality in research and innovation in the Horizon 2020 programme. The aim is to ensure a gender balance in decision-making, the aim is a balance of 40-60 representation with the target of 40 per cent of the underrepresented sex in panels but 50 percent in advisory groups. Regarding civil society organisation one role that they have is to ensure that everybody in society's needs and realities are taken into consideration irrespective of gender, this can be interpreted as that the input by civil society organisations should lead to an output which add value to society through a greater social inclusion in society. For business and industry gender equality is a cross-cutting priority that can affect their 'traditional' structures depending on area of business and or industry as well as how gender-balanced the business or industry currently is.

Within RRI, and in relation to gender balance, what is of interest is how the underrepresented gender is included in the decision-making processes as well as the access the underrepresented gender is both represented and heard by various stakeholders. Thus, one could argue that gender equality and access to participation in, for example, decision-making is an important matter for gender equity especially in the gender equality practice itself. Gender equality is also an important aspect in roles and or tasks assumed and assigned in political institutions, public institutions and bodies, business, industry and civil society organisations as one question here to bear in

mind is how have these roles and tasks been gendered? If the roles and tasks have been gendered how can these be challenged and changed?

The gender dimension within RRI thus provide an opportunity for underrepresented gender to be included in order to achieve a more improved social relevance of results in the research and innovation processes.

5.1.3 Science education

The link between science education⁹ and RRI is that of a structural change to make science education more open and inclusive to the needs of wider society. It links by extending science, that is to say research, and innovation to other parts of wider society and to include a wider understanding of science research and innovations to include social innovations. Science education provide opportunities to expand the skillsets of scientific enquiring skills and scientific competence skills to empower and ensure citizens involvement more fully in the research and innovation policy and decision-making processes. Within RRI science education thus involve six aspects:

- Science education promotes innovative problem-solving and critical thinking skills;
- Further embeds social, economic, and ethical principles in research and innovation¹⁰;
- Promotes engagement in and by wider society as well as an entrepreneurial mindset;
- Empower citizens to participate in science policy making;
- By sharing responsibility between stakeholders in solving social challenges; and
- Facilitates a strong inter- and/or multidisciplinary approach to solving societal challenges and ensures a wider involvement by interested stakeholders.

For the stakeholders this means that policy makers can and need to influence, for example, university curricula by furthering the inclusion of RRI at all levels of education. In relation to the research community, research institutions can open up to collaborations with wider society actors as well as other provider of education through linking research to already ongoing research or new scientific research questions by engaging new networks and as such ensuring it is grounded in wider society. The education community's role is to provide opportunities for training, networking, and resources so that the result is a more educated society. RRI provides the education community with inspiration on how the training, networking, and resources best can be implemented in wider society. One very important stakeholder in the RRI indicator of science education are the civil society organisation as they play a key role in engaging citizens and wider society in research and innovation policies and decision-making. For

⁹ Available here <https://www.rri-tools.eu/science-education#>.

¹⁰ See for example Boly, Morel, and Camargo (2017).

business and industry, a skilled workforce is key, and by facilitate connections between science education strategies and innovations aid the increase of innovation capability within wider society.

The science education dimension's objective within RRI is to provide the tools and language of science to be available to wider society and as a consequence ensure that the citizens has the competence required to participate more fully in the research and innovation processes.

5.1.4 Open access

Open access¹¹ is not only fundamental in relation to RRI it is also the culmination of RRI. Open access is about the dissemination of research for future research and innovations which can benefit the whole of society, it is about finding ways for knowledge to be used by interested parties and actors. Open access to research has been described as a process of science democratisation in which the research process is accessible, accountable, and transparent to both researchers and an interested wider society. Open access thus entails:

- Free access, i.e. that there should be no limit to research findings and results;
- Access to peer-reviewed literature;
- Access to publications and to data;
- Opening up the current [academic] publication system;
- Include more transparency and accountability in the dissemination process of research; and
- Full re-use rights of research.

For the stakeholder groups open access have different input and output results and effects, policy makers for example, has to ensure that an open, wide access to research is a public matter and especially so if the research is funded by public money. At the EU level for the research community this means that any research funded through the Horizon2020 programme have to be available through open access. Within the education community at all levels, that is to say primary, secondary, and tertiary education, an open access to research results and findings ensures knowledge is shared to future researchers and innovators as well as promotes excellence in academia, research and science construction. For civil society open access provides an opportunity to influence future research by being aware of what is currently being in focus for research. For business and industry open access can further nurture open innovation which also will benefit the wider society through co-operation with other stake holders.

¹¹ Available here <https://www.rri-tools.eu/open-access#>.

Open access and availability to research findings is believed to improve the quality of future research an innovation, and to a wider audience who earlier may not have used or access research findings within their activities.

5.1.5 Ethics

Ethics¹² within RRI can be viewed as an actor's responsibility, however it should also be viewed as a collective responsibility as the actor or actors are part of the society. The rationale for this is that science is not seen as value neutral and science has both positive and negative implications on society thus it should all but natural to include various stakeholders in the research process. It is within ethics this inclusion can take place and as a result ethics should therefore be viewed as an inclusive part of research and innovation. The RRI toolkit on ethics list five different features:

- Any research should incorporate integrity in the project, and innovations built upon research needs to ensure that integrity is incorporated in the research;
- Research and innovations based on research should share the responsibility for the impact of the science, that is to say considerations have to be taken of possible results of the research carried out. Questions should be asked around possible impacts upon society as in, for example, the citizens and the environment;
- Ethics is also reflecting on people's ideas and concerns around research and innovation;
- Is the research aligned to social values in society; and
- Ethics should include a deliberation of moral issues with a diversity of actors.

These features within ethics has highlight different relevancies for the various stakeholders. For policy makers and politicians this entail that research and innovation policy that they are responsible for should be consciously developed, and that the policy made is in correspond to the shared values and norms in society as well as meeting the ethical demands of society. For the research community research integrity is key. In an EU perspective research integrity is threefold: research methods, research activities and processes are '(1) guided by standards, guidelines and protocols; (2) open to external scrutiny (for example, ethical bodies extended to societal stakeholders); and (3) open to internal reflexivity'. When research and science has an impact upon society the researcher has a responsibility for his or her research to society, part of this responsibility which is highlighted by the RRI indicators in general and the ethical indicator more specifically. For the educational community the role is to provide tools and training to the citizens in society, these tools should include critical thinking. By having

¹² Available here <https://rri-tools.eu/ethics#>.

knowledge and skills citizens can participate in ethical deliberations in relation to research and innovation. Civil society organisations are also an important stakeholder in relation to the realisation of ethically acceptable research and innovation, this as civil society organisations are aligned with a wide range of interests and groups in society. This ensures that a wider range of values and norms are included in the research and innovation policy process. The final stakeholder group is that of business and industry, in order to embed ethical considerations in the research and innovation processes of industry it is of vital importance that societal and industry actors work together throughout the process.

Within RRI and the ethical indicator one needs to be aware of that different stakeholder will have different needs and there needs to be processes in place to possible conflicts of interest and respect of all contributors. There should also be a balance between stakeholders' risks and values, and here one needs to be aware of that it is not only financial risk but the risk could be in relation to privacy of individuals in society. In addition to the already mentioned the decision-making and implementation processes of research and innovation policies also need to ensure an equitable distribution of value in society as a whole in order to, for example, meet the overall needs and goals of society this so in relation to the RRI indicator of equality and more specifically in relation to gender equality.

The ethical dimension within RRI provides a way for ensuring that research and innovations processes provide high quality results for wider society, and that it is based upon the wider society's shared values.

5.1.6 Governance

Governance¹³ can be viewed as a set of principles agreed upon, in this case in relation to research and innovation activities. Thus, under *governance* can all actions taken by us as individual or as a representative for an organisation of some kind be included, it is our actions that are taken in relation to other stakeholders in society that is of interest. The principles are usually defined by those who finance research and innovation, however through RRI new aspects can be included making the activities more sustainable long-term in a societal perspective as well as ensuring that the research and innovations are implemented and utilised wider in society by including stakeholders from a wider societal perspective. This is where politicians carry the main responsibility in order to ensure that not only are the wider set of governance principles implemented but that they are also followed in order to create a cultural change in society, i.e. to make governance through a RRI perspective work. What does governance as an indicator in RRI then entail?

- It means that there is a collective responsibility among stakeholders for the impact of research and innovation on society;

¹³ Available here <https://rri-tools.eu/governance#>.

- That participatory governance is needed in order to manage with both new and unexpected challenges;
- Transparent and reflective procedures should be included in the research and innovation processes;
- That there is accountability and responsiveness towards society; and
- An anticipation of unintended consequences from research and innovation.

For stakeholder groups this means that policy makers carry the responsibility for guiding the agenda and practice of research funding and thus can influence through this as well as ensure that the RRI indicators are included in research funding. For the research community this entail that

By applying a normative stance within the governance aspect of research and innovation the EU can facilitate change towards norms it has agreed are of vital importance for European society, for example, openness, transparency, accountability and gender equality. The change is partly carried out through RRI by ensuring adherence to the different indicators outlined above – public engagement, gender equality, science education, open access, and ethics – and thus ensuring the inclusion of a wider set of societal norms.

The governance dimension one could argue is the umbrella dimension of RRI as it is within this dimension in which the political expectations, through the policy makers, by ensuring that the measures included in the research and innovation processes are robust, adaptable, responsible, shared, and accountable.

5.2 RRI indicators – a summary in relation to digital transformation

As the DigiTeRRI project had a twin focus on digitalisation processes and digital transformation within the three territories and RRI a summary of RRI indicators in relation to digital transformation is provided below.

Table 2. Dimensions in Relation to Digital Transformation and DigiTeRRI

Dimension	In relation to digital transformation and DigiTeRRI
Public engagement	A platform for information and dialog on the transition processes; highlighting both opportunists and drawbacks, participative approaches through citizens contributions, offering information on training as well as new professional options, that is to say a 'one stop shop' for society within the regions.
Gender equality	Gender equality in relation to income (addressing eventual poverty of women), provide equity of opportunities when it comes to access to training and education programmes in the region, same career options disregarding gender, and a clear commitment in the region to gender equality (plan, strategic document).
Science education	Provide training programs for digitalisation, knowledge 'upgrades' on digitalisation, and the development of education programmes in the regions to have high qualified human resources.
Open access	Includes Infrastructure for repositories for both data and publications, a model for open access to research infrastructure, model for co-operation and research on topics of digitalisation, and the transition of regions and involvement of societal and public institutions. To this dimension the popularisation of science in various forms such as publications and informative programmes should be added.
Ethics	A dialog on digital ethics during and in the processes of transition within the regions, assessments on digital regions, as well as ethical panels especially in relation to digital ethics.
Governance	The governance aspects within the region should both support and monitor the transition processes, the organisation(s) which are in charge of digitalisation continue to monitor improvements of the agreed roadmap and implementation of the roadmap.

As outlined earlier in the text the overall objective the project is to develop a roadmap for a responsible transition of traditional industry regions into digitalised industrial self-sustaining R&I ecosystems by using a Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach. The co-creation of the framework, that is to say the road-mapping process, and the implementation of actions will take place with partners and stakeholders from three territories through an interplay between science, industry, government, and society.

Table 3. Process Dimension and Actions in the Transition Regions

Process dimension	Actions in the transition regions
Diverse and inclusive	Include a wide range of actors in the region in the transition process, and keep maintaining the exchange with others.
Anticipative and reflective	Establish circles, panels and platform in the region to discuss the kind of future we are working, towards and how research and innovation, may shape that future, and develop answers to open questions in the transition process.
Open and transparent	Establish processes by which decisions are reached and science is conducted, so all can see and understand them, establish organisation, institutions or department who are in charge, and include local media in these activities.
Responsiveness and adaptive change	Be open to new development and respond to new findings and circumstances – both in terms of behaviour and structure of organisations, establish measure to react on new events in the change process, keep the process running, nominate organisation/institutions which are in charge of doing that, develop new solution if necessary, and keep track of implementation during the project's timespan.

The co-creation process dimensions have been identified as to be diverse but inclusive, anticipative and reflective, open and transparent, and both responsive and adaptive to change needed throughout the process. During the development of the roadmap and its implementation which is an organic process the interactions and communications between participating stakeholders are of vital importance.

6 ABOUT DigiTeRRI IN GENERAL

DigiTeRRI is acronym of the long project name *Responsible Research and Innovation Approach for Transitioning the Traditional Industry Regions into Digitalised Industry Territories*. The overall objective of the DigiTeRRI project is to develop a framework with specified actions the participating territories need to address in order to transition from traditional industry regions into digitalised industrial regions with self-sustaining and responsible R&I ecosystems. It does so by exploring three aspects or dimensions, firstly the RRI approach and how the RRI approach will support digitalisation transition process by implementing adequate RRI strategies into the regional policies. Secondly, by establishing self-sustaining R&I ecosystem, and thirdly, the degree of maturity of digitalisation in which the territory currently find itself in. The process is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The Main Directions of the Objectives in DigiTeRRI

The project's four target objectives are summarised here and also serve as an outline of how the DigiTeRRI project will proceed:

- 1) The first objective is characterising and mapping the current territorial R&I ecosystems. Thus, Objective 1 provide a qualitative and quantitative stocktaking and mapping of the characteristics of the three territories engaged in DigiTeRRI as outlined in chapter 2. The statuses of the three territories R&I ecosystems, of their digitalisation degrees, and their statuses regarding RRI will be evaluated and characterised. Results will provide a solid empirical analysis and visualised pictures of these three territories for a better understanding of the R&I ecosystems in a larger context in terms of societal, economic, geographic, environment. Results will be documented in a report on contextual R&I ecosystems.
- 2) The second objective is to generate a vision for each of the three territories. The vision will be co-created in workshops the three territories. The three territories Värmland in Sweden, Grand Est in France, and Styria in Austria are each engaged in the project with representatives from the triple helix (local authority, university, industry). Each of the territories has good relations for involving citizens such as employees from the industry in situ or students. One objective here is to move from representative of the triple helix to include civil society and become regions that include representatives from the quadruple helix model.
- 3) The third objective is to develop a roadmap for transitioning into responsible digitalised territories. The design of the roadmap process is based on the mapping and analysis of the R&I ecosystems in the three territories, and refers to the responsible transition of traditional industry regions into digitalised industrial self-sustaining R&I ecosystems by using the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach as outlined in chapter 5. The co-creation of the framework, the road-mapping process, and the implementation of actions will take place with partners and their stakeholders.
- 4) The fourth objective is to implement transitioning activities in the territories. The activities are actions towards a more open, transparent and democratic digitalised R&I ecosystem in each of the participating territories. The measures derived in the roadmap are implemented into various policy instruments, defined during the roadmap process. Changes are monitored and necessary improvements of the degree of digitalisation are performed via feedback loops, and where needed improvements are supported by the exchange of best practices in all three territories.

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